

Kinetic of Reaction with Hydroxide Ions and Solubilities of Salts of Cobalt(III) Schiff Base Complexes in Water—Methanol Mixtures

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Heterocyclic Schiff base complexes of Co^{III} are synthesised. The Schiff bases are tridentate and have dinitrogen and oxygen donors. Solubilities and transfer chemical potentials of perchlorate, thiocyanate and nitrate salts of the Co^{III} complexes in water—methanol mixtures are reported. Transfer chemical potentials for the Co^{III} Schiff base cations are calculated. Trends with solvent composition suggest that preferential solvation varies from negligible to very strong by methanol depending on the ligand structure and hydrophilic/hydrophobic character of the inorganic ions. Kinetics of reactions between hydroxide ion and the Schiff base complexes of Co^{III} in aqueous methanol mixtures follow a rate law with $K_{obs} = K_1 + K_2 [OH^-]$ or $K_{obs} = K_3 [OH^-]$. The analyses of the reactivity trends to initial and transition state show that the small increase of the rate constant is ascribed to a greater effect of solvent on the transition state.

THE solvent structure is important in controlling rates of reactions involving ions in water and water + co-solvent mixture. Though the dependence of the rate constant on the composition of the solvent may be small or dramatic, it is often complicated. In terms of the transition state theory, the complexity reflects the separate influences of changes in solvent composition on initial and transition states. Therefore, independent estimates are thought of the effect of solvent on initial state, and the corresponding effect of solvent on transition state is calculated using both kinetic and initial state data¹⁻⁴.

Solvent effects on reactivities have been analysed into initial and transition state for a variety of organic and inorganic reactions⁵⁻⁸, but no information is available concerning the complete analysis of the solvent effects of reactions involving Schiff base complexes of Co^{III}. The aim of this work is extended to the investigation of the effect of the added co-solvent on the solubilities and kinetics of the reaction of Schiff base complexes of Co^{III} with hydroxide ions. In addition, an attempt has been made to estimate the effect of co-solvent on the initial-transition states. The new solubility data provide the basis for an examination of the effect of size and hydrophilic/hydrophobic character on the solvation of inorganic ions.

A series of Schiff base complexes of Co^{III} have been synthesised. The Schiff base ligands are derived from *o*-aminophenol and 2-pyridinecarbox-

aldehyde (1), 2-acetylpyridine (2) or 2-benzoylpyridine (3).

R = H (1)-poap
R = Me (2)-mpoap
R = Ph (3)-bpoap

Bis(Schiff base) cobalt(III) cations decompose slowly in sodium hydroxide and Co(OH)₃ precipitates. The feature of this reaction is the attachment of a hydroxyl group to the position of the coordinated Schiff base molecules. This converts the ligands from hydrophobic to predominantly hydrophilic character. Few studies of the alkaline hydrolysis of chelate have been reported. A lack of the activation parameters, plus varying degree of Co—O bond cleavage during the hydrolysis of the chelate thwarts a discussion of the factors influencing the rates. However, interpretation of these results are complicated by the observation that the presence of oxygen is required to promote hydrolysis in basic solution^{9,10}.

The rate of the reaction between sodium hydroxide and bis(Schiff base) cobalt(III) cations was measured for a variety of hydroxide ion concentrations and water—methanol mixtures at 298 K.

Results and Discussion

The complex salts were characterised by their electronic absorption spectra and elemental analysis (Table 1). The molar conductances (in ethanol) of these complexes are in the range $37-45 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Microanalysis and molar conductance data confirmed that the Schiff base complexes of Co^{III} were in monocationic form produced from the two anionic Schiff base ligands^{1,2}.

Kinetics of the reaction between the cobalt complexes and hydroxide ion were followed spectrophotometrically at 298 K. Rate constants were calculated from the dependence of absorbances on time, characterising the decrease in concentration of the cobalt complex with time. This dependence was monitored for at least 2.5 half-lives for reactions in solutions.

The dependence of K_{obs} on base concentration is linear with intercept for the $[\text{Co}(\text{mpoap})_2]^+$ cation but there is no significant intercept of the correlation line for the $[\text{Co}(\text{poap})_2]^+$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{bpoap})_2]^+$

cations. Hence, the rate of the reaction follows the kinetic equation (1) for the first cation, and kinetic equation (2) for the other cations,

$$K_{\text{obs}} = K_1 + K_2[\text{OH}^-] \quad (1)$$

$$K_{\text{obs}} = K_2[\text{OH}^-] \quad (2)$$

where K_{obs} is the experimental first order rate constant measured under condition, where $[\text{OH}^-] \gg [\text{complex}]$, and K_1 and K_2 are the corresponding first and second order rate constant respectively. Values of K_1 and K_2 computed from a least-mean-squares analysis of the dependence of the observed first order rate constants on base concentration at each aqueous-methanol proportion are presented in Tables 2-4. The change in the activation barrier $\Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$ for the three complexes from water to aqueous methanol are derived in Tables 2, 3, 4.

Concentrations of saturated solutions of cobalt complexes in water + co-solvent methanol are reported in Table 5. These data are the starting point for the calculation of transfer chemical potentials of salts and ions.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				λ_{max} nm (E_{max})
	C	N	H	Co	
$[\text{Co}(\text{poap})_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	53.28 (54.03)	13.50 (13.13)	3.88 (3.75)	10.76 (11.07)	490 (8 400)
$[\text{Co}(\text{mpoap})_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	53.23 (53.88)	12.82 (12.10)	4.35 (4.49)	9.94 (10.19)	460 (6 250)
$[\text{Co}(\text{bpoap})_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	60.20 (59.91)	10.40 (9.70)	4.21 (4.44)	7.82 (8.18)	440 (5 840)

 TABLE 2 - FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT (K_{obs}) FOR REACTION BETWEEN $[\text{Co}(\text{mpoap})_2]^+$ AND OH^- IONS IN METHANOL - WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Vol % MeOH	$K_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1})$ for NaOH (mol dm ⁻³)					K_1 $\times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	K_2 $\times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$
	0.066	0.130	0.200	0.266	0.330			
0	2.4	3.9	4.9	6.1	7.3	1.33	0.18	0.00
20	4.1	6.1	8.0	9.9	11.8	2.24	0.29	-1.17
40	6.1	9.1	11.9	14.6	17.7	3.34	0.43	-2.14
60	8.7	12.5	16.3	20.3	23.9	4.97	0.57	-2.84

 TABLE 3 - FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT (K_{obs}) FOR REACTION BETWEEN $[\text{Co}(\text{poap})_2]^+$ AND OH^- IONS IN METHANOL - WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Vol % MeOH	$K_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1})$ for NaOH (mol dm ⁻³)					$K_2^\ddagger$ $\times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\Delta \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$
	0.0066	0.013	0.020	0.0266	0.033		
0	1.5	3.0	4.6	5.9	7.5	2.21	0.00
20	2.0	4.2	6.0	8.2	10.4	3.03	-0.78
40	3.2	6.4	8.8	13.2	16.3	4.85	-1.95
60	4.6	8.6	13.1	17.4	21.8	6.66	-2.73

TABLE 4—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT (K_{obs}) FOR REACTION BETWEEN $[Co(bpoap^-)_2]^+$ AND OH^- IONS IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Vol % MeOH	$K_{obs} (10^{-4} s^{-1})$ for NaOH (mol dm ⁻³)					$K_s \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$	$\Delta\Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$
	0.066	0.130	0.200	0.266	0.330		
0	3.1	6.1	9.1	12.1	15.4	0.46	0.0
20	3.7	7.2	10.8	14.3	18.1	0.55	-0.4
40	4.3	8.3	12.2	16.4	20.4	0.62	-0.7
60	5.1	9.9	14.7	19.7	24.7	0.70	-1.2

TABLE 5—DERIVATION OF TRANSFER CHEMICAL POTENTIALS FOR Co^{III} SCHIFF BASE CATIONS FROM SOLUBILITY MEASUREMENTS ($T = 298$ K)

Vol % MeOH	0	20	40	60
$\Delta_l^\ddagger (ClO_4^-)^a$ kJ mol ⁻¹		0.1	-0.1	0.2
$\Delta_u^\ddagger (SCN^-)^a$ kJ mol ⁻¹		-0.6	-0.9	0.2
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger (NO_3^-)^b$ kJ mol ⁻¹		1.1	1.8	3.0
	$[Co(mpoap^-)_2]ClO_4$			$\epsilon (\lambda = 460 \text{ nm}) = 6250$
$10^3 s$	1.400	2.960	5.600	11.840
$\Delta_u^\ddagger$ (Salt) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-3.7	-6.9	-10.6
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-3.8	-6.8	-10.8
	$[Co(mpoap^-)_2]SCN$			
$10^3 s$	0.616	1.410	2.576	4.800
$\Delta_u^\ddagger$ (Salt) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-4.1	-7.1	-10.7
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-3.5	-6.2	-10.9
mean $\Delta\mu^\ddagger [Co(mpoap^-)_2]^+$ kJ mol ⁻¹		-3.6	-6.5	-10.8
	$[Co(poap^-)_2]ClO_4$			$\epsilon (\lambda = 490 \text{ nm}) = 8400$
$10^3 s$	0.449	0.574	0.752	1.057
$\Delta_u^\ddagger$ (Salt) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-1.2	-2.5	-4.2
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	1.3	-2.4	-4.4
	$[Co(poap^-)_2]SCN$			
$10^3 s$	0.988	1.500	2.001	2.604
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Salt) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-2.1	-3.5	-4.8
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-1.5	-2.6	-5.0
mean $\Delta\mu^\ddagger [Co(poap^-)_2]^+$ kJ mol ⁻¹		-1.0	-2.2	-4.3
	$[Co(bpoap^-)_2]ClO_4$			$\epsilon (\lambda = 440 \text{ nm}) = 5840$
$10^3 s$	0.020	0.079	0.267	1.336
$\Delta_u^\ddagger$ (Salt) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-6.7	-12.7	-20.6
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-6.8	-12.6	-20.8
	$[Co(bpoap^-)_2]NO_3$			
$10^3 s$	0.169	0.558	1.563	6.036
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Salt) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-6.9	-11.0	-17.7
$\Delta\mu^\ddagger$ (Cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	0	-7.0	-12.8	-20.3
mean $\Delta\mu^\ddagger [Co(bpoap^-)_2]^+$ kJ mol ⁻¹		-6.9	-12.7	-20.5

s = Solubility (mol dm⁻³). Ref. 6. ^bRef. 11.

Solubility measurements have been used to determine free energies of transfer for individual cations M^{n+} from water into water+co-solvent mixtures using a sparingly soluble salt M_mX_n where the free energy of transfer of the anion X^{m-} is already known. The free energy of transfer of the salt is determined by using the equations¹³⁻¹⁵,

$$\Delta\mu^\ddagger (M_mX_n) = RT \ln (K_w/K_s) \quad (3)$$

where, K is the solubility of M_mX_n in water (w) and in water+co-solvent mixture(s). The free energy of transfer of the cation $\Delta\mu^\ddagger (M^{n+})$ can then be calculated from equation (4) using the known values of $\Delta\mu^\ddagger (X^{m-})$

$$\Delta\mu^\ddagger (M^{n+}) = \frac{\Delta\mu^\ddagger (M_mX_n) - n\Delta\mu^\ddagger (X^{m-})}{m} \quad (4)$$

The Co^{III} Schiff base salts of the perchlorate, thiocyanate and nitrate anions are sparingly soluble in water and in water-rich methanol mixtures. They are, thus, suitable for the estimation of single ion transfer chemical potentials of cobalt cationic complexes from water into such mixtures via solubility determination. Transfer chemical potentials for these salts were calculated on the assumption that the ratio of mean activity coefficients in water and aqueous methanol was unity in all cases. As discussed earlier¹, in the present context this is probably satisfactory ($Z_+Z_- \leq 3$) using the transfer chemical potentials for the various cationic complexes derived on the TATB and TPTB assumption^{16,17}.

The results illustrated in Fig. 1 can mainly be rationalised in terms of overall charge on each complex and hydrophobic nature of the present ligand. Hydrophobic ligands, such as heterocyclic Schiff bases lead to stabilisation as methanol content increase. Phenyl group is considerably more hydrophobic than methyl group and proton; thus, the results show preferential solvation by methanol which becomes more rich as ligand size increases. As increase in the ligand size, parallel hydrophobic character occurs, resulting from both replacement of proton by methyl and phenyl groups.

Fig. 1. Dependence on vol% of single ion transfer chemical potentials for Co^{III} cations in water-methanol mixtures.

For a solution which is dilute in reactant, the rate constant K_2 is related, using transition state theory, to the molar Gibbs function of activation $\Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger$, expressed on the *c*-scale at temperature *T*.

$$\Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow X_2) \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; T) = RT \ln [K_2(\text{aq})/K_2(x_2)] \quad (5)$$

where second order rate constants for a given reaction are $K_2(\text{aq})$ in aqueous solution and $K_2(x_2)$ in a solvent mixture (X_2 is the mole fraction of organic solvent).

The effect of added organic solvent on rate constants for reaction in aqueous solution between cation complex M^+ and anion OH^- can be understood in terms of the impact of co-solvent on the reference chemical potentials of these ions and of transition state $\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger$. The effect of added solvent is described using the equation¹⁸,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow X_2) \Delta^\ddagger G^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; P; T) &= \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow X_2) \mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; P; T) \\ &- \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow X_2) \mu^\ddagger (\text{complex}; c\text{-scale}; P; T) \\ &- \Delta(\text{aq} \rightarrow X_2) \mu^\ddagger (\text{OH}^-; c\text{-scale}; P; T) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Combination of kinetic data, solubility data and transfer chemical potentials yield the effect of solvent on the transition state according to equation (6) (Table 6, Figs. 1-4). Here we use the

TABLE 6—INITIAL STATE—TRANSITION STATE ANALYSIS OF SOLVENT EFFECTS ON REACTIVITY TRENDS

Vol % MeOH	20	40	60
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{OH}^-)$	0.2	0.1	1.6
$[\text{Co}(\text{mpoap})_2]^+ + \text{OH}^-$			
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{Cation})$	-3.6	-6.5	-10.8
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{ts})$	-3.8	-6.4	-9.2
$\Delta\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger G^\ddagger$	-1.2	-2.1	-2.8
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{ts})$	-5.0	-8.5	-12.0
$[\text{Co}(\text{poap})_2]^+ + \text{OH}^-$			
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{Cation})$	-1.0	-2.2	-4.3
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{ts})$	-1.2	-2.1	-2.7
$\Delta\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger G^\ddagger$	-0.8	-1.9	-2.7
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{ts})$	-2.0	-4.0	-5.4
$[\text{Co}(\text{bpoap})_2]^+ + \text{OH}^-$			
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{Cation})$	-6.9	-12.7	-20.5
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{ts})$	-7.1	-12.6	-18.9
$\Delta\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger G^\ddagger$	-0.4	-0.7	-1.2
$\Delta\mu_{\ddagger}^\ddagger (\text{ts})$	-7.5	-13.3	-20.1

The energies of transfer parameters, initial state and transition state are kJ mol^{-1} .

concentration scale, and so the reference state for a given solute *j* is a solution where $C_j = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and the activity coefficient $\gamma_j = 1.0$; at constant solvent composition, $\lim (C_j \rightarrow 0) \gamma_j = 0$. In this study, the pressure *P* is ambient and *T* is 298 K.

The analyses of kinetic results for reaction of Schiff base complexes of Co^{III} with hydroxide ions provide an example of the situation (Figs. 2-4). The small increase in the rate constant of $[\text{Co}(\text{poap})_2]^+$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{mpoap})_2]^+$ cations as the

Fig. 2. Initial state-transition state analysis of reactivity trends for $[\text{Co}(\text{mpoap})_2]^+$ in water-methanol mixtures.

Fig. 3. Initial state-transition state analysis of reactivity trends for $[\text{Co}(\text{poap})_2]^+$ in water-methanol mixture.

Fig. 4. Initial state-transition state analysis of reactivity trends for $[\text{Co}(\text{bpoap})_2]^+$ in water-methanol mixtures.

methanol content increases is ascribed to predominant stabilisation of the transition state. However, the analysis for reactivity trend of $[\text{Co}(\text{bpoap})_2]^+$ cation shows the initial state and the transition state which are stabilised on increasing the methanol content with small increase in the rate constant. This is due to the slightly greater effect of solvent on the transition state.

Experimental

All the chemical were of Aldrich and B.D.H. The Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of the appropriate *o*-aminophenol and 2-pyridine-carboxyaldehyde, 2-acetylpyridine or benzoylpyridine for 2 h in ethanol. The solutions of the Schiff base and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed in the ratio 2 : 1, when oxidation took place with bubbling air. The resulting solid complex after slow evaporation of alcohol, was washed with 50% ethanol-water mixtures.

The sparingly soluble perchlorate and thiocyanate salt of the Co^{III} complexes were prepared by saturating the nitrate salt solutions with sodium perchlorate and potassium thiocyanate. Methanol was treated with Mg and I_2 , refluxed, distilled and the mixed solvents were made up before mixing. Solubilities were determined by thermostating a generous excess of the solid with the appropriate solvent and with frequent agitation in the ultrathermostat HAAKE circulators (F3-K). Precautions were taken to avoid heating of aliquots of saturated solutions before dilution and to prevent any solid material being carried through with samples of saturated solutions.

Kinetics of the reactions were measured by following the dependence of absorbance on time using 10 mm silica cells in the thermostated cell compartment of a CECIL 599 spectrophotometer. Chemical reactions were monitored in solutions held at constant ionic strength using sodium chloride.

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